

Research Article

Ceritera Kuih: Anthropomorphism Representation in the Digital Literacy of Storytelling

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Abstract: *Today's culture of innovation has been hailed as an important step toward creating a sustainable nation. This is demonstrated by Malaysia's Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Indicators. According to the ninth target indication, it highlighted about build resilient infrastructure, promote comprehensive and sustainable industry, and promote innovation. As a result, the implementer of this study's development of innovation in Learning and Teaching (PdP) is in line with the ninth goal, which requires for our country recommence to innovate and establish sustainable culture associated to the innovative product's. The Ceritera Kuih product is a storytelling innovation in the form of an interactive electronic book (e-Book) that represent anthropomorphism characters concept throughout the storytelling. This e-book was created using the ADDIE model, which consists of the following five steps: analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation. The application of this innovation can assist students in fostering a culture of creativity when creating digital short stories by incorporating interactive features. The students are not only able to compose innovative short stories and learn about the digital literacy process, but they may also foster a culture of creativity through the production of recipe videos as a digital content (using Malaysian Kuih) in the interactive e-book.*

Keywords: Storytelling; Digital Literacy; Anthropomorphism.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Digital literacy act as the tool to encourage students to enhance their ability and skills towards creative writing in The Fourth Industrial Revolution (IR 4.0). Autonomous decision making by cyber physical systems using machine learning enabled by cloud computing as a hallmark of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The Digital Literacy means to be computer literate; is to be able to comprehend and make effective use of information offered in a variety of digital formats and from a variety of digital sources (Gilster, 1997). While Spires, Paul & Kerkhoff (2018) explained that a wide range of digital reading and writing skills are required for digital literacy, including those for words, texts, visual displays, motion graphics, audio, video, and multimodal forms.

According to Creer (2018), in her research mentioned that youth use digital media in their everyday literacy practises, and a failure to adopt new technology in the classroom could result in a disconnect between their everyday and college-assessed literacy practises. Furthermore, students that are well-versed in the digital world will make efforts to gather and evaluate relevant data, as well as to comprehend, express, and articulate ideas in the digital age (Berta Dinata, 2021). Thus, with the student's exposure of the digitalization era, the ideation towards digital literacy among students in the classroom triggered the process to innovate the *Ceritera Kuih* e-book. This cutting-edge e-book generates digital literature for future archival purposes as a reference for students and lecturers. Students may

compile their creative stories about the anthropomorphic characters in the narrative that based on the traditional *Kuih-Muih* in Malaysia. Aside from that, the e-book has a creative video on the recipe of Malaysian *Kuih* to make the innovation unique on one platform as a way to teach digital literacy in the 21st century.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study used a method of qualitative through content analysis of the case study towards *Ceritera Kuih* as the innovation product of the e-book. The *Ceritera Kuih* product is a storytelling innovation in the form of an interactive electronic book (e-Book) that represent anthropomorphism characters throughout the storytelling. To produce the e-book for the digital literacy among students in a classroom, I applied the ADDIE Model to achieve the production of the innovation of *Ceritera Kuih* storytelling. Welty (2007) present his study on 'The Design Phase of the ADDIE Model' stated that the model is a general concept for curriculum development. It gives high-level direction to educators, software engineers, and others as they create and improve learning products. There are five phases on the model as a guideline that are (1) Analyze, (2) Design, (3) Develop, (4) Implement and (5) Evaluation. For the purpose of the innovation, I targeted the students of 3D Animation Program in my classroom that learn the sub creative writing subject preferably known as STD 20043 Conceptual Design (*Reka Bentuk Konsep*).

Diagram 1. The ADDIE Model as the framework of *Ceritera Kuih* e-book innovation.

3. FINDINGS

The innovation of the digital literacy known as *Ceritera Kuih* is based on the representation of anthropomorphic characters concept throughout the narrative structure. The short stories depicted the food culture in Malaysia through the eight stories of popular *Kuih-Muih* in this country such as *pau*, spring roll (*popiah*), doughnut, *samosa* and potato curry puff (*karipap kentang*), *putu piring* and *kaswi*, tang yuan, *onde-onde*, *kuih lapis* and *tapai*. The creation of the short stories in *Ceritera Kuih* is as Table 1 below:-

Table 1. The title of the short stories of *Ceritera Kuih* e-book

No	Title	Description
1	<i>Melankolik, Pau & Oyen</i>	This narrative follows a young man who like pau and owns a cat named Oyen. His tragic past, on the other hand, causes the remembrance of his favourite <i>kuih</i> , pau, to lead to a gloomy and sorrowful memory.
2	<i>Dendam Popiah</i>	In this tale, a young man who enjoys stealing food from the school canteens finally receives his punishment for his misdeeds.
3	<i>Sombongnya Donat!</i>	This story tells about the life of a doughnut who has an interesting character, makes himself arrogant, and likes to belittle other beings.
4	<i>Samosa VS Karipap Kentang</i>	Samosa is very popular among the <i>Kuih-Muih</i> , but the appearance of Potato Curry Puff has ruined its popularity and caused Samosa to hold a grudge.
5	<i>Onde-Ondeku Sayang</i>	This is the story of a grandmother and her granddaughter who are both adore with <i>onde-onde</i> . One day, the granddaughter bought an <i>onde-onde</i> to visit her grandmother in the hospital, but it was lacking the essential ingredient of <i>gula melaka</i> filling.
6	<i>Keinsafan Putu Piring</i>	Queen <i>Putu Piring</i> is one of the magnificent <i>kuih</i> , but her deception during the war with the <i>Kaswi</i> people has challenged her leadership as head of state.
7	<i>Tang Yuan</i>	This story is about a traditional Chinese dessert called Tang Yuan. It was made by a grandmother for her grandson, but when something went awry, the grandson was determined to make the dessert the way his grandmother told him to.
8	<i>Kesalan Angkuh Kuih Lapis</i>	<i>Kuih Lapis</i> criticized <i>Si Tapai</i> , who had a foul odor, since she thought her beauty was so lovely. <i>Si Tapai</i> ultimately proved to be the hero who rescued <i>Kuih Lapis</i> from the invasion of black ants.

3.1 Narrative Structure in *Ceritera Kuih* e-Book

The narrative structure used in this innovative product of *Ceritera Kuih* e-book uses Freytag's Pyramid concept. This narrative concept consists of elements such as exposition, inciting incident, rising action, climax, falling action and resolution and denouement. According to Chey (2021) in her article of 'Learning Freytag's Pyramid' she claims that as the audience, we appreciate stories that follow a natural progression of events and provide hints at deeper themes as they are revealed. She added, story arc creates character compassion. It immerses the spectator in the character's world and their issues. Narrative structure persuades audiences to believe in a concept, a cause, and a product or service, while making them feel like they are contributing to something greater.

3.2. Character Concept in Ceritera Kuih e-Book

The character's concept from the eight short stories in the *Ceritera Kuih* e-book is based on the anthropomorphic characteristic to make this creative work distinctive and entertaining. Among the anthropomorphic character in the short stories including *pau*, spring roll (*popiah*), doughnut, *samosa* and potato curry puff (*karipap kentang*), *putu piring* and *kaswi*, *tang yuan*, *onde-onde*, *kuih lapis*, and *tapai*. Rajora (2017) explained on the term of anthropomorphism refers to the attribution of human characteristics, feelings, and intentions to non-human creatures. Respectively, the terminology is derived from the Greek words "anthropos" and "morphe," which mean "human" and "form". The anthropomorphism representation in the *Ceritera Kuih* e-book will be discussed further in the discussion section.

4. DISCUSSION

Based on the artistic work of this short story as a product of innovation, it was discovered that the anthropomorphism characteristics influenced the development of the character concept of the eight short stories that were produced. The analysis from Table 2 below depicted the representation of anthropomorphic characters in the *Ceritera Kuih* e-book.

Table 2. The Anthropomorphism Representation in the *Ceritera Kuih* e-book

No	Title of Short Stories	Anthropomorphic Characters	Description
1	<i>Melankolik, Pau & Oyen</i>	<i>Pau</i>	Human characteristics to non-living things (objects or forms) The character Pau appeared in the young man's dream and then gave words of encouragement to the young man to continue his life after the past tragedy.
2	<i>Dendam Popiah</i>	<i>Popiah Gergasi</i>	Human characteristics to non-living things (objects or forms) The Giant <i>Popiah</i> character who binds <i>Abu Samah</i> because of the actions of him who likes to steal and be mischievous.
3	<i>Sombongnya Donat!</i>	<i>Si Donat</i> <i>Burung Murai</i> <i>Pohon Ajaib</i>	Human characteristics to objects, animal or forms <i>Si Donat</i> , the main character, is stunning yet haughty. The Bird (<i>Burung Murai</i>) was fascinated by <i>Si Donat's</i> beauty but was despised by <i>Si Donat</i> . While the Magical Tree is a plant character that is given human behavior through its advice to <i>Si Donat</i> .
4	<i>Samosa VS Karipap Kentang</i>	<i>Samosa</i> <i>Karipap Kentang</i>	Human characteristics to non-living things (objects or forms) In this story, the character of Samosa holds a grudge against Potato Curry Puff to the point that he is willing to endanger the life and safety of Potato Curry Puff. While the Potato Curry

5	<i>Onde-Ondeku Sayang</i>	<i>Onde-Onde</i>	Puff has good behavior and a pure heart.
Human characteristics to non-living things (objects or forms)			
<i>Kuih Onde-Onde</i> characters express their displeasure with humans' dishonesty in producing <i>kuih-muih</i> such as Onde-Onde. The confectioner man in this story forgets to use brown sugar as the filling.			
6	<i>Keinsafan Putu Piring</i>	<i>Permaisuri Putu Piring</i> <i>Puding Diraja</i> <i>Bangsa Kaswi</i> <i>Penasihat Seri Muka</i>	The four characters mentioned have been given human characteristics as rulers in a fantasy country. This story tells about the conflict between Queen <i>Putu Piring</i> and the <i>Kaswi</i> tribe.
Human characteristics to non-living things (objects or forms)			
<i>Tang Yuan</i> characters in this narrative exhibit human characteristics such as cuteness, biting, talking, and motions. Tang Yuan has assisted the grandchildren in making a delightful dessert like his grandmother has always made.			
7	<i>Tang Yuan</i>	<i>Tang Yuan</i>	Human characteristics to non-living things (objects or forms)
Human characteristics to non-living things (objects or forms)			
8	<i>Kesalan Angkuh Kuih Lapis</i>	<i>Kuih Lapis</i> <i>Semut Hitam</i> <i>Si Tapai</i>	<i>Kuih Lapis</i> feels that she is the most beautiful being. She is so arrogant and likes to insult <i>Si Tapai's</i> weakness that it stinks, until finally, when <i>Kuih Lapis</i> is attacked by <i>Black Ants</i> , <i>Si Tapai</i> saves him from the threat.

THE INNOVATION: CERITERA KUIH E-BOOK

5. CONCLUSION

In the era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, where computers and other digital technologies play an increasingly important role, digital literacy serves as an incentive for students to develop their writing skills (IR 4.0). The Fourth Industrial Revolution is distinguished by the autonomous decision-making of cyber physical systems enabled by machine learning and cloud computing. Thus, this innovation of *Ceritera Kuih* e-book helps students improved their skills in the production of creative writing short stories with the digital tools such as Heyzine application for the e-book. In addition to writing creative short stories and gaining insight into the digital literacy process, students can use the interactive e-book to create digital content in the form of recipe videos (using Malaysian Kuih), potentially fostering a culture of creativity. Anthropomorphic character's through the eights short stories in this innovation makes the product unique and inspired.

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